

THE CONTENT OF FORMING LEADERSHIP QUALITIES IN OLDER PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20744709>

Abstract. *This article examines the formation of leadership qualities in older preschool children as a pedagogical and social necessity within preschool education and everyday social practice settings. It analyzes national preschool education standards, the Ilk Qadam curriculum, developmental processes, and play-based, reflective, and collaborative approaches. The analysis shows that leadership qualities can be developed through social communication, emotional intelligence, creative activities, decision-making tasks, responsibility, motivation, and confidence-building games. Role-play, team games, problem-solving activities, and creative group tasks help children practice initiative, cooperation, self-expression, and responsible choice-making. The findings emphasize that systematic guidance by teachers and parents, emotionally supportive environments, and age-appropriate educational technologies are essential for preparing children for collective activity, social adaptation, and future leadership.*

Keywords: *preschool-aged children, leadership, leadership qualities, leadership abilities, leadership skills, formation.*

Introduction

Resolution No. PQ-4312 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 8, 2019, “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030,” defines the goals and priority areas for developing the preschool education system. The purpose of this Concept is to develop mechanisms for access to quality preschool education, which is an important source ensuring the formation of all spheres of a child’s life and activity [6].

The priority areas for developing the preschool education system are as follows: further improvement of the regulatory and legal framework in the field of preschool education; creation of conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic, and physical development of preschool children; expansion of coverage with quality preschool education, ensuring equal access to it, and development of public-private partnership in this field; and introduction of innovations, advanced pedagogical technologies, and information and communication technologies into the preschool education system [6].

The Concept establishes that improvement of the educational and upbringing process should be carried out on the basis of assessing the level of children’s development and their readiness for general primary education, as well as their social, personal, emotional, speech, physical, and creative development.

The purpose of the “State Standard for Preschool Education and Upbringing,” approved by Resolution No. 802 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 22, 2020, is to organize the preschool education system on the basis of modern requirements, to raise children as healthy and comprehensively mature individuals, to introduce effective forms and methods of education and upbringing into the educational process, and to educate a spiritually

mature generation. It also aims to introduce and organize control over mandatory minimum requirements concerning the scope, content, and quality of the educational process, the construction and equipment of preschool educational organizations, and the organization of healthy nutrition and safety for preschool children [9].

The “State Standard for Preschool Education and Upbringing” defines requirements for the development of early and preschool-aged children. The aim of the state requirements is to educate a spiritually mature and intellectually developed person in the preschool education system, taking into account the socio-economic reforms being carried out in the country, the advanced experience of foreign countries, achievements in science, and modern information and communication technologies.

The improved “Ilk Qadam” state curriculum defines the competencies of the “Social-Emotional Development” area. After completing educational and upbringing activities in the field of “Social-Emotional Development,” a 6- to 7-year-old child has an understanding of his or her own “self” and the role of other people in the environment of life activity. The child manages his or her emotions and expresses them appropriately according to the situation; distinguishes the emotions of others and responds to them appropriately; communicates appropriately with adults and peers according to the situation; and finds constructive ways out of difficult situations [11]. It can therefore be seen that, in the above-mentioned regulatory documents, the socialization of the child’s personality and the development of leadership qualities in the child are important social necessities [11].

Methods

The main processes of preschool children’s development are multifaceted, and various methods and activities are important for introducing and forming them. These processes encompass the child’s psychological, moral, physical, social, and intellectual development. The main developmental processes include the following:

Physical development. Formation of children’s motor skills, including fine and gross motor skills. Through physical activity, children are introduced to balance and movements, as well as complex movements such as dance and sports games.

Intellectual development. Mental development through introduction and acquisition of skills. Formation of language and speech, learning new words and concepts, and forming scientific concepts on the basis of mathematics, science, and other knowledge areas.

Social development. Formation of children’s ability to work in a team and interact with others. Awaken a sense of respect and responsibility and developing emotional empathy. Acquiring experience through interactions, games, and roles in the social environment.

Emotional development. Becoming familiar with emotions, understanding and managing one’s emotional states. Developing emotional stability and self-control skills. Teaching children to recognize their emotional states in different situations and to interact properly with others.

Creative and artistic development. Developing the child’s imagination and creative thinking through creative activities such as art, music, drawing, and modeling. Manual work and activities that influence imagination, such as making flowers from paper and coloring.

Language and communicative development. Correct and complete use of language, development of speech, and correct pronunciation of words and sentences. Participation in group games, conversations, and storytelling. Various games, work activities, educational and creative activities, and free communication have a major influence on the development of preschool children.

The methodology for developing leadership qualities in older preschool children has been improved on the basis of revitalizing the content of the social environment with play technologies based on real-life situations that serve to increase emotional intelligence, gradually adapting children's psychological state to leadership activity, and extrapolating reflective conversations and collaborative learning methods. This methodology serves to develop children's initiative, responsibility, culture of communication, teamwork skills, and decision-making abilities. In explaining the main concepts, we present the content as follows. Leadership qualities are a person's ability to influence others, unite a team around a common goal, show initiative, and assume responsibility. Emotional intelligence is a person's ability to understand and manage his or her own feelings and the emotions of others and to use them in effective communication. Play technologies are methods of forming knowledge and skills through role-playing, plot-based, and didactic games that ensure children's active participation in the educational process. Revitalization in education is the process of increasing the effectiveness of the existing educational environment by enriching it with modern approaches, interactive methods, and content. Adaptation is the process by which a child becomes psychologically and socially adjusted to a new type of activity, in this case leadership. A reflective conversation is a form of dialogue aimed at analyzing the child's own activity, behavior, and feelings. Collaborative learning is a process of acquiring knowledge on the basis of group cooperation and is based on mutual assistance, exchange of opinions, and collective decision-making. Extrapolation is the process of adapting and applying existing scientific ideas and methods to new conditions and circumstances. In forming leadership qualities in older preschool children, these aspects play an important role. In addition, during the preschool period, under the influence of the intensive development of speech, communication, and group activities such as play, speech, visual, and other types of activity, children's leadership potential becomes more clearly and stably manifested. At the same time, however, children often perform leadership functions in a fragmentary, imitative, or temporary manner.

The extrapolation of reflective conversations and collaborative learning methods is considered one of the effective psychological and pedagogical mechanisms for forming leadership qualities in older preschool children.

Collaborative learning methods are based on organizing children's cooperative activity. In these methods, each child participates as an important member of the team and contributes to achieving a common goal.

Extrapolation means adapting and applying reflective conversations and collaborative methods to various pedagogical situations and types of activity.

Studies on the development of qualities such as independence, initiative, leadership, inquiry, goal orientation, independence, caution, perseverance, mutual assistance, kindness, and conformity in older preschool children show that, at preschool age, individual components of personality structure begin to develop, a personality capable of leadership activity begins to take shape, certain special qualities become clearly manifested, and the first steps are taken in the formation of leadership qualities. Proper guidance from parents and educators plays a decisive role in this process.

The age requiring special attention is preschool age. Researchers, including educators, psychologists, and others, show particular interest in this age period because it is precisely during this period that personality development continues, the range of actions carried out jointly with other people expands, and qualities of personality such as leadership, positive orientation, aspiration toward goals, initiative, responsibility, independence, and discipline develop. In

addition, life values and attitudes that determine the child's behavior in various life circumstances are formed.

According to physiologists, by the age of seven, the parts of the brain responsible for programming, regulating, and controlling complex mental activity specific to humans have not yet fully formed. This is reflected in the characteristics of children's behavior, organization of activity, and emotional sphere typical of the early school age. During this period, children are neurologically and psychologically vulnerable.

The extrapolation of reflective conversations and collaborative learning methods into the pedagogical process forms an innovative methodological basis for developing leadership qualities in older preschool children, supporting their socio-emotional development, and preparing them for collective activity.

Results

The formation of leadership qualities in older preschool children is important, and in this process their social, emotional, and intellectual skills can be developed through various activities and games. Leadership qualities such as responsibility, the ability to influence others, confidence, and teamwork can develop in a child's everyday activities and games.

The main processes influencing the development of leadership qualities are carried out in the following areas:

1. Social and communicative development. Relationships and group games: through games, children learn to work in a team, reach agreement with others, and take into account the needs of team members. In this process, children form leadership qualities because, in group games, a child learns to express his or her opinion, guide others, and adapt to them.

2. Emotional development. Emotional intelligence: developing children's ability to understand their own emotional states and to respond empathetically to the emotional states of others is one of the main qualities for leadership. Through emotional intelligence, children learn to manage themselves, remain calm in difficult situations, and help others.

Problem solving: helping children solve problems in various situations and supporting them in making decisions are also aimed at forming leadership qualities. Children must learn to make calm and rational decisions in difficult situations.

3. Creative and artistic development. Creative activities: art, dance, music, and other creative activities help children freely express their thoughts and inspire others. Creativity creates opportunities for developing new ideas and leading their implementation.

Manual work and teamwork: when children are given opportunities to discuss and implement their dreams and ideas with others through manual work and games, this helps develop leadership skills.

4. Choices and decision-making. Decision-making: allowing children to manage themselves and make small decisions develops their independence. For example, in games, they may make decisions about the direction in which the team should move.

Responsibility and ethics: teaching children to be responsible and to observe truth and justice toward themselves and others develops their ability to make fair and objective decisions.

5. Motivation and inspiration. Inspiration: a leader seeks to inspire children and to be an example for them in achieving their goals. Children need to learn the skills of inspiring others by helping them, supporting them, and showing confidence in them.

Different methods of motivation: by showing children ways to support goal orientation, encourage their actions, and reward them, a leader stimulates children’s motivation to work and make decisions.

6. Self-presentation and sense of confidence. Confident self-expression: in order to form leadership qualities, it is important to teach children to present themselves confidently and to develop communication and connection with others. All of this provides reliable support for the child’s future leadership abilities.

These processes influence the child’s social, emotional, and intellectual development and create opportunities for forming leadership qualities in children.

Discussion

Forming leadership qualities in older preschool children through play is one of the effective ways to develop children’s social, emotional, and intellectual skills. For children, play is not only recreation but also helps develop important qualities such as learning, relationships, responsibility, and leadership.

The following methods and activities are effective in forming leadership qualities through play. Play methods for forming leadership qualities in older preschool children are briefly explained in Table 2.1.1.

Table 2.1.1

Types of games	Possibilities of games
Role-playing games	Role-playing games allow children to take leadership in various situations. In their games, children may play the role of an educator or group leader.
Team games	Team games help develop social skills in children while also helping to form leadership characteristics.
Creative games and activities	Creative activities such as art, drawing, and modeling can develop children’s leadership abilities by forming creative skills and inspiring others.
Problem-solving games	In forming leadership qualities, it is important to help children make decisions and solve problems in difficult situations.
Thinking and decision-making games	A leader child clearly determines the direction in which others should act.
Developing self-confidence	Leadership is primarily connected with the ability to express oneself confidently and lead the team in one’s own direction.

1. Role-playing games allow children to take leadership in various situations. For example, the roles of “Educator” or “Friend” may be used. In their games, children may play the role of an educator or group leader. This gives them the opportunity to guide others, give instructions, and make decisions.

The roles of “Doctor” or “Police Officer” allow children to work in a team, help others, and lead them. They feel themselves to be responsible persons and learn to make moral decisions.

2. Team games help form social skills in children and, at the same time, help develop leadership characteristics. Working in a team teaches a child to reach agreement with others, move toward a goal, and share responsibility. For example, “Dividing into teams” games involve

dividing children into small groups and appointing a leader for each group. The leader manages his or her team and guides it toward completing the tasks. This helps children develop the ability to manage projects and inspire the team.

3. Creative games and activities. Creative activities can develop children's leadership abilities through art, drawing, modeling, and similar activities that help form creative skills and inspire others. For example, children may be given the opportunity to create a gallery as a group and present their work. Through teamwork in play, distribution of specific tasks, and implementation of these tasks, children's skills as team leaders can be improved.

4. Problem-solving games. In forming leadership qualities, it is important to help children make decisions and solve problems in complex situations. For example, games may be organized in which children are required to make collective decisions and solve problems in difficult situations. This teaches children to make correct decisions, lead, and take responsibility. Creating various events and situations for children and, accordingly, helping them to work actively to solve them and to manage projects supports the formation of these skills.

5. Thinking and decision-making games. A leader child clearly determines the direction in which others should act. In order to form these skills, it is necessary to help children make decisions.

"Finding a solution to a problem" games present children with a problem or situation and ask them to find a solution. This helps children develop independent thinking and decision-making skills.

6. Developing self-confidence. It is important to help children express themselves confidently through games. Leadership is primarily connected with the ability to express oneself confidently and lead the team in one's own direction. For example, rewarding and encouraging children for each small success helps develop in them a sense of confident self-expression.

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